

Afrofuturism, African-American Music and Female Agency

by [Pablo Markin](#) · Published 25/02/2019 · Updated 27/02/2019

Montréal 03 octobre 2013 – Neptune’s Moons (Kaie Kellough & Jason Sharp - Dark Matter), October 3, 2013 | © Courtesy of blogocram/Flickr.

On November 10, 2018, Nathalie Aghoro has published an [article](#) entitled “Agency in the Afrofuturist Ontologies of Erykah Badu and Janelle Monáe” in [Open Cultural Studies](#).

A Blog Post by Pablo Markin.

In her [article](#), Nathalie Aghoro has explored how Afrofuturist musicians Erykah Badu and Janelle Monáe “design alternate projections of world/subject relations through the development of artistic personas with speculative background narratives and the fictional emplacement of their music within alternate cultural imaginaries” (330). The scholar has concentrated on the identitarian fluidity of these black female artists to [approach](#) “instances of othering and exclusion by associating these with science fiction tropes of extraterrestrial, alien lives to [also] express topical sociocultural criticism” (330). [...]

Based on her [study](#) of Badu and Monáe’s works, such as music albums, Aghoro concludes that, “[b]uilding on motherhood tropes and womanist ideas, Badu simultaneously affirms and redefines black womanhood while Monáe’s gender-bending performances deconstruct or rather overwrite female/male dichotomies” (339).

According to Aghoro, the works of these performers “prove that social change needs visions and utopian ideas that popular culture at its best is able to provide” ([339](#)).

By Pablo Markin

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